

Socio-Cultural Impact Of Urbanization On Rural Students' Academic Performance: Empirical Evidence From Quaid-I-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan

Asif Nawaz¹, Dr. Sadia Saeed², Abid Rasool³, Shahid khan⁴, Haji Ur Rahman⁵, Mauz Khan⁶

Abstract

The transition from rural to urban environments can significantly impact students' academic trajectories. This study delves into the sociocultural factors influencing the academic performance of rural students in an urban university setting. By examining the interplay of various social identities through an intersectional lens, this research seeks to understand the challenges and opportunities faced by these students. Furthermore, the research emphasizes how urbanization affects rural students' academic performance and well-being, focuses on sociocultural experiences, educational opportunities, and the processes of adaptation. The Study investigates how different social identities interact to influence students' experiences in urban environments, by using Kimberlé Crenshaw's theory of intersectionality. With a sample size of 383 students, the study was conducted at Quaid-i-Azam University Islamabad, adopted a stratified random sampling design. The researcher manually distributed an in-depth survey for data collection, and IBM SPSS Statistics version 22 was used for analysis. Results show that there is a significant trade-off among rural and urban locales, metropolitan regions providing benefits for learning and access to a wide range of services, despite possible social and economic costs. The study highlights the challenges that rural students encounter when adjusting to urban life, such as troubles with preserving cultural identity, understanding social norms, managing stress, and handling expenditures. Overall, the study underlines how essential it is for educators and decision-makers to provide inclusive educational settings that accommodate the various requirements of students moving from rural to urban settings.

Keywords: Urbanization, Academic performance, Student experiences, Cultural diversity, cultural change, education, and Educational equity.

1. Introduction

Various factors affect students' academic performance, which is assessed by their total grade point averages (GPAs) in each course. While each student has different choices and learning styles, however, few characteristics that might influence how well they perform academically.

¹B.S Scholar, School of Sociology, Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad Pakistan. Email: asifnawazkhattak15@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, School of Sociology, Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad Pakistan. Email: ssaeed@qau.edu.pk

³Ph.D Scholar, School of Sociology, Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad Pakistan. Email: abid@soc.qau.edu.pk

⁴B.S Scholar, Department of Social work, University of Peshawar Pakistan Email: shahidkhansocialworker@gmail.com

⁵Lecturer, Department of Sociology, Hazara University Mansehra Email: hajirahmanburki@gmail.com

⁶Visiting Lecturer, Department of Archeology, University of Malakand Email: mauzkhan425@gmail.com

These include extracurricular activities like sports and university clubs, social events, and romantic relationships, all of them could interfere the academic responsibilities (Konuk et al., 2023). The lack of access to necessary resources, such technology, or peaceful places to study, could hinder academic success, therefore limitations in resources also play a part. Furthermore, time management issues can interfere with sleep patterns and study time, cultural festivals, late night calls, and online gaming have an adverse effect on academic performance (Ternenge & Torkuma, 2023).

Urbanization, is the growing number of people living in cities, creates an obstacle for education. Although there is opportunity for development, its quick rise from 2% of the world's population in 1900 to a predicted 72% by 2050 raises issues with fairness in education and sustainability, perhaps extending the difference between rural and urban regions (J. Li et al., 2023). The United Nations (2023) has pointed out that the complex effects of urbanization have an influence on social structures, cultural practices, as well as demography. It is projected that 68% of people on World will live in urban areas by the year 2050, including big cities like Shanghai, Delhi, and Tokyo being classified as megacities. However, urbanization could promote development in the nearby rural territories, promoting technological improvements, economic expansion, and the decrease of poverty. Higher literacy rates, easier access to social services, more job possibilities, and vital infrastructure are among advantages that urban residents frequently enjoy (UN, 2023).

Due to economic concerns, there are several challenges associated with urbanization for students moving from rural regions to metropolitans. Urban areas suffer with a growing population and overburdened infrastructure. Due to a lack of opportunities in rural areas, Pakistan is experiencing fast urbanization, which is causing people to migrate to urban centers in search of greater possibilities (Imran et al., 2022). The current educational difference is widening because of this movement, with rural illiteracy rates particularly in developing countries rising to two or three times higher than those in metropolitan areas (UNESCO, 2023). Millions of rural youngsters are forced into child labor because of this inequality, which particularly impacts women. Academic pressure, environmental shifts, and technological disparity await students moving to metropolitan areas. These factors could contribute to mental health issues including anxiety and depression, underscoring the need for more widespread access to education (Borah et al., 2022).

Stress has an impact on students of both genders and is a common cause of academic challenges such as anxiety about exams, difficulties with understanding, and loss of interest (Borah et al., 2022). Findings indicate that rural educational institutions have less access to technology and learning tools than their urban counterparts, which contributes to the "digital divide" and further complexity. There is also a difference in the comfort and confidence of urban and rural teachers in using technology in the teaching space. Urban instructors are often more excited about using technology in their classrooms (Wang, 2021).

Students at urban educational institutions face difficulties because of urbanization, such as racial prejudice and poverty. Educational institutions in urban areas are often faced with difficult problems that could affect the academic, social, and emotional growth of the students. Furthermore, minority students could have additional difficulties because of the dominant culture in the classroom (Shankar-Brown, 2021). Financial limitations may also harm urban pupils by preventing them from accessing necessary resources like sports equipment, libraries, and certified teachers (Amiri & El Karfa, 2022).

The educational atmosphere has become more complex by unequal access to high-quality English language instruction across regional and socioeconomic barriers. Studies indicate that students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds learn academic abilities more slowly than

those who come from better socioeconomic backgrounds (Amiri & El Karfa, 2022). On the other hand, being in multilingual situations can have advantages such as improved intellectual growth, enhanced communication skills, and enhanced multitasking abilities (Amiri & El Karfa, 2022).

The obstacles faced by international students adjusting to new educational institutions throughout their time in university include managing cultural differences, behaviors, and expectations (Ali et al., 2021). Initial phases might include feelings of irritation and a tendency to find comfort in cultural groupings. However, eliminating early obstacles and assimilating into the new cultural environment are frequently necessary for effective adaptation. Using this approach may develop a respect for the foods, traditions, and customs of the host culture. Returning to one's native culture after adaptation might result in "reverse culture shock," underscoring the difficulties associated with cultural shifts (Denen, Asaju, & Bott, 2021),

For effective adjustment and academic achievement, one must develop one's self-confidence and ask for help from peers, organizations, and loved ones (Ali et al., 2021). Effective coping strategies include having an open line of communication, participating in social activities, and using constructive self-talk. On the other hand, avoidance is seen to be the least successful tactic when dealing with challenges (Abbasi et al., 2020). Faculty and educational institutions may help students adjust by offering tools and coaching that address both academic and cultural problems.

Students face a wide range of difficulties because of urbanization, including inequality in resource availability, poverty, and racial prejudice in institutions. Students from minority backgrounds who encounter dominant educational environments may find it more difficult to develop intellectually, socially, and emotionally because of these obstacles. Inequalities in socioeconomic status may widen the achievement gap by preventing certain students from accessing high-quality education, which could cause them to learn skills more slowly (Amiri & El Karfa, 2022). On the other hand, multilingual settings may be advantageous as they promote cognitive growth, multitasking, and communication. The new university system presents early problems for international students adjusting to cultural differences, but effective adaptation often entails overcoming these barriers and embracing the new culture, which may result in a respect for the host environment (Ali et al., 2021). However, this process of adjusting can be difficult, and returning students could experience "reverse culture shock." To overcome these obstacles and succeed academically, it's essential to develop one's self-confidence, ask for help, and use constructive coping techniques. To help students overcome academic and cultural obstacles, educational institutions are essential (Al-Houdalieh & Sauders, 2022).

Students at higher education institutions face an extensive range of issues because of the growth of urbanization, especially those who come from rural backgrounds. According to study by Ashifa (2022) and others, such students face a variety of challenges because of the changing social and cultural setting caused by urbanization. Adjusting to shifting cultural norms, managing environmental pressures, negotiating technology divides, and overcoming educational variations are some of these issues. Moreover, the increasing speed of globalization makes it even more essential to understand and deal with the complex issues that urban students experience, particularly those related to their academic performance, mental health, and cultural adjustment. This issue becomes worse by the increasing gap in educational options in rural and urban areas, which is further exacerbated by factors like resource scarcity, racial prejudice, and poverty. Consequently, the goal of this research is to examine the many obstacles that result from the sociocultural effects of urbanization on rural students' academic performance and overall well-being. This study focuses specially on:

How urbanization influences the socio-cultural experiences of rural students and how these experiences impact their academic performance?

The educational opportunities and challenges faced by rural students due to the process of urbanization.

The adaptation process of rural students as they navigate the challenges posed by urban environments.

The rest of the article contains the following sections. Section 2 contains a literature review, section 3 explains the theoretical framework, section 4 is based on data and methodology including Research site, data collection method, and inferential statistics, section 5 contains the result discussions, and Section 6 depicts the conclusion of the study.

2. Literature Review

Gender roles and academic achievement are significantly shaped by socio-cultural norms, which are impacted due to variety of elements in cultures, including history, religion, and environment. Tradition frequently connects femininity with domesticity and caring, and masculinity with strength and material achievement (Onea, 2023). As therefore, unique gender roles develop, with women often handling household management and males typically taking primary responsibility for employment and family provision. But it's important to remember that these functions vary geographically and aren't always consistent (Neculasai, 2022). According to J. Li et al. (2023), gender discrimination resulting from these norms continues to be a significant obstacle to obtaining equal rights and opportunities.

These roles with males having more authority and women largely maintaining household roles are frequently maintained in traditional societies. However, examples of women taking part in significant choices suggest that there may be more room for agency in some situations, even in conventional settings (Ugwu & De Kok, 2020). Despite concerns that urbanization might strengthen hierarchical systems. It gives women possibilities as well. Greater access to both official and informal work can be found in urban settings, which might challenge inflexible social norms that view women as dependents. Furthermore, women are better equipped to make educated decisions about fertility when they have access to healthcare facilities in urban areas (Sharkey et al., 2018).

The world is changing quickly and becoming a more integrated global village due to causes like the growing internet and social media (Abbasi et al., 2020). The sense of global community has been developed by advances in technology that have permitted contact across long distances, driven by increases in knowledge, education, and interest in global concerns (Chou, 2019). There are advantages and disadvantages to this trend of growing urbanization, which is marked by migration from rural to urban areas and population expansion in urban centers. People move to cities in search of better living circumstances and employment prospects; occasionally, this means giving up their own language and culture in the process of adjusting to new surroundings (Singh, 2018). The attraction forces of employment possibilities, education, and better access to facilities and services are driving this urban population development, which is fostering industrial advancement, social transformation, and economic expansion. However, there are drawbacks to rapid urbanization as well. In Pakistan, for example, rapid migration and population growth put a strain on government resources, lead to problems like unemployment and poor infrastructure, and force people to deal with the difficulties of adjusting to urban life, which may present problems like a lack of jobs or financial hardship (Jabeen et al., 2017).

According to Wahid et al. (2021) there are two drawbacks to urbanization, or the increase in the number of people living in cities. Rapid urbanization is caused by migration to cities due to industrialization and the attraction of job prospects, which are sometimes seen as scarce in rural regions (Yasin et al., 2012). Although this movement provides people with hope for a better life, there are serious drawbacks as well. According to studies, there is a possibility that fast urbanization may change social and cultural environments, affecting everything from personal values and family structures to housing and clothes (Wahid et al., 2021). In addition, uncontrolled urbanization has the potential to contribute to pollution-related environmental problems and lower living standards in impacted communities. The desire for improved living conditions, access to healthcare and education, and freedom from constrictive societal structures are typically the driving forces behind this phenomenon, which is especially common in developing countries (Abbas & Ansari, 2019). However, the effects go beyond the environment, as crowding in vital facilities like educational institutions, hospitals, and transportation networks becomes a significant issue that affects both public areas and personal encounters. In conclusion, urbanization brings opportunity, but it also brings with it significant social, cultural, and environmental issues that must be carefully considered and managed (Rahim et al., 2018).

Due to its accessibility and well-built infrastructure, urbanization provides benefits to education. More access to skilled instructors and maybe a more productive learning environment can be achieved by metropolitan institutions with larger student populations and greater resources (Konuk et al., 2021). In addition to providing more social and economic possibilities, increased access to education also empowers people and promotes development (Abdullah et al., 2021). It is essential to recognize that these advantages might not be enjoyed by everyone, and more study is required to fully understand the subtle ways that urbanization affects educational possibilities in various settings (Mendoza 2020).

Although cultural variety is beneficial to growth and development, different beliefs and goals are possibly developed in rural and urban areas, which may influence academic performance (Chen, 2021). Compared to metropolitan environments, rural places could place less value on academic accomplishment, underscoring the complex connection between culture and educational performance. To produce a distinct cultural fusion, old customs usually combine with new surroundings during cultural interchange, such as that which migrants go through when adjusting to new cities (Esitti, 2023). This demonstrates how culture is dynamic and how important it is to fully understand the many ways in which it affects people. Rapid urbanization, however, can put cultural heritage at risk and needs drawing a careful balance between welcoming progress and preserving customs. In conclusion, navigating the complex interactions between culture and academic performance in a globalized world requires acknowledging the various perspectives shaped by environment and culture, promoting intercultural understanding, and establishing a balance between progress and tradition (Al-Houdalieh & Sauders, 2019).

Studies like Dodsworth's (2022) indicate that nutrition plays an essential part in academic engagement, behavior, and thought processes; balanced diets are associated with these benefits. However, Dodsworth pointed out that kids from low-income families are more likely to eat unhealthy foods, which could harm their academic performance. Mekonnen and Ayele (2020) highlight once more how critical it is to address food insecurity and guarantee that students have access to nutritious meals to support their general wellbeing and academic ability. By examining how campus eating venues affect dietary decisions and highlighting the ways in which cost, taste, and accessibility affect students' food preferences.

Even if it might not seem relevant, research like that reveals an unexpected link between dress code and academic performance (Law and Istook, 2022). Studies indicate that students' self-perception, which is impacted by their clothing choices, might have an impact on their involvement and associate professional clothes with higher participation in class. Ofori et al. (2021) go deeper into the variables affecting students' clothing decisions, highlighting elements including peer pressure, comfort, affordability, climate, and self-expression. It's interesting to note that Saravanan and Nithyaprakash (2020) highlight the significance of fashion in students' self-identity and indicate that their capacity to express themselves via clothing choices may be impacted by financial limitations.

A student's academic experience is shaped by a complicated network of circumstances that happen outside of the classroom. While addressing issues about dominance and diversions, the co-education discussion also recognizes the potential benefits of single-sex and co-educational environments (Orfan & Niazi, 2021). Although co-curricular activities may promote growth and academic success, their effects might differ. Peer groups have a big impact on behavior and grades. Both good and negative characteristics can affect behavior. Unquestionably, socioeconomic status matters since children from diverse backgrounds have varying access to resources. International students have difficulties while adjusting to a new environment, but universities provide a variety of support services to help with them (Martirosyan et al., 2019). In conclusion, a variety of factors that go well beyond the boundaries of traditional academics influence a student's performance (Moldes et al., 2019).

While existing research explores various factors influencing academic performance, a gap remains in comprehensively analyzing the interplay between these factors. This study aims to bridge this gap by investigating how nutrition, clothing choices, co-education, co-curricular activities, peer groups, socio-economic background, and adaptation to new environments collectively shape student performance. By considering these factors in a holistic manner, the study seeks to provide a more nuanced understanding of the complex web of influences shaping academic success.

3. Theoretical Framework

The concept of intersectionality, as defined by Kimberlé Crenshaw, looks at how different social identities such as gender, race, and socioeconomic status overlap and influence a person's experience. Understanding the complexity of education in urban regions is made easier with the aid of this idea. Students from various backgrounds have different advantages and problems. Academic performance is impacted due to a variety of factors, including social networks, cultural norms, unequal resource distribution, and even access to nutritious food. Intersectionality recognizes the potential advantages of metropolitan surroundings, such as access to a variety of extracurricular activities and high in nutrients food, while simultaneously acknowledging that marginalized groups may face compounded disadvantages. Education professionals and legislators may establish more inclusive learning settings that help every student realize their academic potential by having a better knowledge of these interrelated social factors.

4. Methodology

Description of Study Site:

The research was carried out at Islamabad's Quaid-I-Azam University. The selection of this educational institution was made based on the heterogeneous student body, which covers different parts of Pakistan. Socioeconomic diversity is ensured by the university's merit-based admissions policy, which includes students from less advantaged backgrounds. The goal was

to provide a thorough picture of Pakistan's youth population by concentrating on a culturally diverse environment. The study focuses on the various issues that arise from the sociocultural effects of urbanization on rural students' academic performance and overall well-being.

Data and Sampling Technique:

There are 13559 students registered at the university, according to Times Higher Education. For the study, Campus Management System (CMS) data was used to provide a more precise figure. The Quaid-I-Azam University in Islamabad's Campus Management System (CMS) reports that 5091 rural students are enrolled overall, in a total domicile wise. To ensure equitable representation of faculties, degree levels, and genders within the target population, a stratified random sampling strategy was used. Using the stratified random sampling technique, the representative sample size for each stratum was then calculated using the stratified random sampling formula, Overall sample size / Total population * Subgroup population. With a strong representation of the study population, the final sample size of 383 was established by considering the overall enrollment.

Stratified Random Sampling Formula: Total Sample Size / Entire Population * Population of Subgroup

Figure 1: Sample Size of Quaid-I-Azam University, Islamabad

Source: Times Higher Education

Data Collection

Comprehensive methodology was used in the data gathering process, with a well-structured questionnaire including both multiple-choice and open-ended questions. The questionnaire was

individually distributed by the researcher, while additionally giving support when needed. To ensure precise and efficient processing for quick assessment, the gathered data was analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 22. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, while inferential statistics made it easier to generalize findings from the sample to the broader population.

Ethical Considerations:

From an ethical point of view, the study remained committed to respecting moral principles for the whole research period. Strict protocols were put in place to guarantee participant data privacy. Participants gave written consent, assuring that their personal information would be used only for research purposes, kept secret, and not disclosed to outside parties. Administrative consent was acquired for participation.

5. Results

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the survey findings, which show a complicated trade-off between the urban and rural surroundings. More than 70% of people believe that metropolitan areas are excellent learning environments with an extensive number of specialized teachers and libraries as well as a variety of educational options. But there is a condition to this benefit. More than 74% of respondents recognize the difficulties faced by female students in rural locations, raising the possibility of societal obstacles and a lack of opportunities for higher education in those places. Surprisingly almost 70% of respondents also think that urbanization benefits rural students, citing more access to facilities and exposure to a greater variety of information in cities. When it comes to consuming food, a similar tendency shows up. While more than 78% of respondents think that supermarkets and specialized shops make healthy food more accessible in urban areas, a significant 72% also address the possible drawback of this perception, specifically the possibility of higher costs for this better food in urban areas. Overall, the results indicate that, though often at an expense, cities have advantages in terms of education and may even food diversity. Despite these drawbacks, food prices may be lower in rural locations. A cost-benefit analysis based on personal needs and priorities appears to be involved in selecting between different environments.

Table 1:

Statement	Yes (%)	No (%)
Respondents' views about urban environment affects learning	70.4	29.6
Challenges faced by rural female students	74.3	25.7
Urbanization benefits for rural students	69.9	30.1
Availability of healthy food in urban environment	78.6	21.4
Cost of food in urban environment	72.6	27.4
change food habits and choices in urban environment	79.7	20.3
cost of fashionable clothing in urban environment	70.3	29.7
Communication with the opposite gender in coeducation	59.2	40.8
Teachers support at urban environment	67.1	32.9
Handling stress in urban life	41.4	58.6
Impact of financial resources and learning	86.4	13.6
adjustment to various socio-cultural norms in urban environment	49.8	50.2

maintaining cultural identity in urban areas	54.7	45.3
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The results of the study show a fascinating interaction between individual behaviors and the urban setting. City living has a significant influence, as seen by the high ratings for difficulties changing eating choices (79.7%) and keeping up with fashion trends (70.3%). Good nutrition is frequently affected by the increased accessibility of fast food and the fast-paced lifestyle of cities, and maintaining fashionable clothes can be costly due to social demands and the continually developing fashion scene. It's interesting to see that the communication score (59.2%) is less precise. Either the greater ease with which individuals connect with persons of the other sex in coeducational settings, or the possible difficulties in negotiating romantic relationships or unwanted approaches in a more private urban context, might be the cause of it. Finally, the teacher support score (54.7%) indicates that although most respondents felt sufficiently supported, a significant number of respondents may have encountered the drawbacks of the bigger class sizes and heavier workloads that are frequently connected to urban educational institutions. Because of the high paced, competitive, and sometimes lacking green areas found in metropolitan surroundings, a significant percentage (86.4%) suffer from stress. People may experience overload and a loss of connection to the natural world because of this continual stimulus. Moreover, financial resources are essential to education in cities (67.1%). Students from diverse socioeconomic origins may face unequal opportunities due to the high expense of educational resources and extracurricular activities, as well as unequal access to quality educational institutions.

Almost half (49.8%) said it was difficult to adjust to different standards, perhaps because they were unfamiliar with the new habits and had to overcome linguistic or cultural hurdles. This may have two drawbacks. The exposure to varied standards may also be a source of enrichment and widen one's viewpoint, even though some (40.8%) find it difficult to preserve their own cultural identity within the urban melting pot, perhaps because of pressure to integrate or a lack of specialized cultural support networks.

Inferential Analysis

The cross tabulation and chi square test is used to assess a certain hypothesis using a statistical technique called inferential analysis. It is used to evaluate how effectively sample results may be generalized to a larger population and to draw conclusions about a cause-and-effect relationship.

Hypothesis Testing

Null Hypothesis: (H_0) There is no significant relationship between cultural elements of urbanization and academic performance.

Alternative Hypothesis: (H_1) There is a significant relationship between cultural elements of urbanization and academic performance.

Table 2 Cross tabulation of cultural factors, urban environment and academic performance

	Urbanization and academic performance of rural students					Total
	negative	very negative	positive	very positive	not at all	

Urbanization and cultural elements influence	to a very large extent	88	13	121	2	0	224
	to a large extent	0	0	0	84	0	84
	to a moderate extent	0	0	0	48	0	48
	to a small extent	0	0	0	22	0	22
	not at all	0	0	0	1	4	5
Total		88	13	121	157	4	383

The above cross-tabulation is used to test a hypothesis on the relationship between rural students' academic performance and cultural aspects of urbanization. The alternative hypothesis (H1) argues that there is a significant connection between these variables, contrary to the null hypothesis (H0), which argues that there is no relationship at all. Urbanization and cultural factors' effects on academic performance are cross tabulated in the table according to their relative strengths. The rows display the equivalent influence on academic performance, ranging from extremely bad to highly positive, while the columns show varied levels of urbanization and cultural aspects. It is clear from looking at the statistics that most respondents (224) think that cultural factors and urbanization have a significant influence on academic performance. Among them, 88 respondents believe the impact to be unfavorable, 13 strongly disagree, 121 agree, and two very agree. This implies that a significant portion of people believe there is a direct correlation between urbanization, cultural components, and academic performance.

Moreover, the data indicates that 84 respondents think urbanization has a very favorable impact on academic performance, but none of them regard it to be highly influential. In addition, 22 respondents think it has little influence, and 48 feel it has a moderate influence. Just 5 respondents say that urbanization has no effect at all on students' academic achievement. The alternative hypothesis (H1) is strongly supported by the cross-tabulation data, which shows a considerable correlation between rural students' academic performance and cultural aspects of urbanization. The evidence comes from the large percentage of respondents who believe that urbanization and cultural factors have varied degrees of influence on academic performance. As a result, it is reasonable to draw the conclusion that cultural aspects of urbanization and academic performance among rural students are significantly correlated, supporting the alternative hypothesis (H1) and rejecting the null hypothesis (H0), given the compelling evidence from the cross-tabulation.

Table 3 Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	679.193 ^a	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	530.794	16	.000
N of Valid Cases	383		
a. 12 cells (48.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .05.			

The results of the Chi-Square tests used in this research provide insight into the relationship between the variables under study, that is, the cultural elements of urbanization and rural students' academic performance. With 16 degrees of freedom and a Pearson Chi-Square value of 679.193, the asymptotic significance level of .000 indicates a very low likelihood that these results could have been obtained by chance. Likewise, at a significance level of .000 and with 16 degrees of freedom, the Likelihood Ratio Chi-Square value is 530.794. When testing hypotheses, both test statistics are usually used to evaluate the independence or relationship between categorical variables. The statistically significant Chi-Square values indicate a strong relationship between cultural elements of urbanization and the academic performance of the rural student group. The number of categories minus one is represented by the degrees of freedom in both tests, indicating the independence of responses within these categories. There is a strong correlation between these variables, as evidenced by the low p-values (around zero), which further supports the rejection of the null hypothesis.

The cross-tabulation study shows a strong relationship between rural students' academic performance and cultural elements of urbanization. This is further demonstrated by the fact that a significant number of respondents saw influence to differing degrees, supporting the alternative hypothesis while challenging the null hypothesis. In addition, this association's significance is confirmed by the chi-square tests, such as the Likelihood Ratio and Pearson Chi-Square.

6. Discussion

Findings from surveys and literature reviews together provide insight into the detailed relationship between rural students' academic performance, cultural elements, and urbanization. The research study underlined how diverse students are affected by sociocultural norms, gender roles, and fast urbanization. These elements provide the background knowledge needed to comprehend both the opportunities and challenges experienced by students in both urban and rural settings.

Gender norms that may be harmful to academic performance, especially for females in rural regions, are kept alive by deeply rooted sociocultural norms that are shaped by a complex interaction of culture, religion, and past tradition. The findings of the survey provide evidence, since a significant percentage (74.3%) recognize the challenges experienced by female students residing in remote areas. This research highlights how urgent it is to eliminate these gender-based educational hurdles, particularly in rural areas where these ancient beliefs may be even more established. However, a more detailed picture of how urbanization affects student outcomes is also presented by a survey. Even though most (69.9%) recognize the difficulties experienced by rural students, they think that urbanization may provide those advantages. This indicates that there might be benefits to urbanization for rural students regardless of the known challenges. The survey results provide insight into the complex web of benefits and drawbacks

related to urban and rural environments for educational attainment, building on previous research that highlights the global trend of urbanization driven by technological advancements and rising populations (Singh, 2022). Cities are considered dynamic hubs of knowledge because they provide a wide range of educational options. This is according to the survey's findings, which indicate that people view metropolitan settings as advantageous for the growth of students. Limited educational opportunities are a substantial obstacle for pupils in rural locations, demonstrated by a survey. This leads to a difficult trade-off. As previously said, 70% of respondents may think that urbanization benefits rural students; however, cities can also present barriers because of their greater variety of educational options. The result highlights the significance it is to consider each person's requirements and goals when deciding between urban and rural learning environments.

Drawing from prior investigations that highlight the worldwide urbanization trend fueled by population growth and technology breakthroughs (Mendoza 2019), our survey results shed light on the complex web of benefits and drawbacks related to obtaining an education in urban and rural areas. Urban areas, which are often seen as vibrant hubs for education, are attractive due to their variety of educational options; in fact, more than 70% of participants in our study felt that learning occurs best in urban settings (already noted). This is consistent with studies conducted by Abdullah et al. (2021) and Konuk et al. (2022), both highlight the need for better access to resources and skilled instructors in urban institutions. However, the report also highlights notable difficulties that students encounter in both environments. Although there may be more educational opportunities in cities, 86.4% of respondents said that mental health was a concern in metropolitan settings, raising the possibility of negative effects. Furthermore, the necessity of extensive support networks in urban educational settings is highlighted by the high cost of living, which is a problem that exists everywhere in cities. This leads to a challenging trade-off: cities may provide more opportunities for education, but they also bring in certain difficulties. In addition, rural settings may provide less of these financial and social responsibilities, even though they may lack diversity in education. Furthermore, this contradiction highlights how important it is to consider personal needs and preferences when deciding between urban and rural learning environments. Cultural diversity is a significant factor influencing educational experiences in an intriguing interaction between the research that has already been done and the result of survey. The literature review by Chen (2020) explores further the possible impact of cultural values on academic achievement; however, the reality demonstrated by survey is more crucial. Adjusting to different cultural standards is difficult for over half of the respondents (45%). This highlights how complexly cultural background and intellectual achievement are related. The constant struggle between tradition and progress further complicates this dynamic. Urbanization is accelerating due to population increase and technological developments (Chou, 2013). According to Al-Houdalieh & Sauders (2019), it could cause difficulties for cultural heritage. This issue is acknowledged by the results of our survey, which highlights the value of promoting multicultural understanding. In conclusion, balancing the possibilities that come with growth with the preservation of the traditions that define our identities is crucial for negotiating the complicated relationship between culture and academic achievement.

Literature study delves deeper into the elements that affect academic performance. It examines a variety of issues, such as socioeconomic position (Bhat et al., 2016), co-education (Ebrahimi & Yarahmadzahi, 2018), dress code (Law & Istook, 2019), and nutrition (Dodsworth, 2021). These concerns are supported by our survey results, which underscore how student experiences are impacted by the learning environment—in such a case, metropolitan areas. In relation to metropolitan surroundings, over 80% (79.7%) of respondents recognized a change in eating habits, and over 70% (70.3%) noted a shift in clothing choices. These results imply that a

student's move to an urban setting may have an impact on areas of their lives outside of the classroom. The survey also highlights the fact that key elements that influence academic achievement are location-independent and include financial resources, stress levels, cultural identity, and teacher support. Using chi-square tests for inferential analysis, our study indicated the complex relationship between rural students' academic performance and cultural aspects of urbanization. Strong evidence of a statistically significant association between these parameters was produced by this investigation. The image that emerged from the cross-tabulation data was interesting: a significant percentage of participants said that they thought the degree of urbanization and the cultural factors at work had different effects on academic achievement. The statistical argument for rejecting the null hypothesis is strengthened by the low p-values obtained from the chi-square testing. In other words, these low p-values indicate that it is exceedingly improbable that the correlation between academic success and cultural aspects of urbanization is the result of random chance. This strong data shows how crucial it is to take cultural factors into account within the larger urbanization context to fully understand rural students' academic experiences.

To sum up, this comprehensive conversation highlights how complicated the connection is between urbanization, cultural components, and academic achievement. Urban surroundings present issues related to gender norms, stress, and cultural changes, even though they also offer advantages in terms of education and different options. The results highlight the significance of specialized interventions and support networks to deal with these issues and ensure fair educational opportunities for students in both urban and rural environments.

7. Conclusion and Policy Suggestion

Studying socio-cultural norms and how urbanization affects many aspects of life offers a sophisticated perspective on the complicated dynamics involved in social change. Numerous major themes show the complexity of these events and their effects on people and communities throughout the literature assessment and analysis. This thorough investigation offers insightful information to scholars, educators, and policymakers on the relationship between urbanization trends, cultural dynamics, and educational outcomes.

The literature highlights an ongoing problem about the broad effect of socio-cultural norms on gender roles and academic performance. Gender discrimination is frequently sustained by deeply rooted societal expectations, which obstruct equality and restrict people's chances for growth. On the other hand, urbanization is a revolutionary force that destroys traditional thinking and opens doors for women's empowerment by giving them more access to healthcare, work, and educational opportunities. To promote gender equality and eliminate structural inequities within educational institutions, specific strategies are necessary due to the dynamic nature of gender roles and their interaction with socio-cultural elements. Moreover, the urbanization phenomena have an expand dimension, presenting prospects as well as difficulties for people and societies. Cities provide advantages like better access to educational resources, a wider range of career options, and cultural enrichment, but they also come with drawbacks like increased living expenses, worse environmental conditions, and social inequalities. The results of the study highlight the difficult trade-offs people must choose between when deciding where to live. They also show how important it is to consider each person's requirements and priorities when making these selections. Furthermore, urbanization has an impact on a range of lifestyle aspects, such as food preferences, fashion choices, and social interactions, in addition to academic domains. Rapid sociocultural change and a wide range of cultural influences seen in urban settings may destroy long-standing conventions and practices, forcing people to adjust to new circumstances. Socioeconomic inequality and the difficulties of adjusting to urban life

highlight the necessity of removing structural obstacles to guarantee that everyone has fair access to resources and support networks.

The inferential analysis highlights the major impact of societal transformations on educational results by providing strong evidence of an important relationship between academic performance among rural students and cultural features of urbanization. The statistical results highlight the significance of targeted approaches to address the sociocultural factors that influence academic success and establish inclusive learning settings that support students' overall growth. In conclusion, the thorough analysis of urbanization patterns, socio-cultural norms, and how they affect academic performance highlights the importance of comprehensive approaches to address the variety of issues that face students individually and in their communities in a world that is changing quickly. To support the academic success and general well-being of all people, regardless of background or circumstance, policymakers, educators, and researchers must give top priority to projects that advance gender equality, address socioeconomic disparities, and create inclusive urban environments. Urbanization has the capacity to alter communities, but societies must first embrace diversity, develop acceptance, and advance social justice to create more equal and sustainable futures for future generations.

7.1 Policy Suggestions

Adopt laws that support gender equality in education, such as programs that aim to eliminate discrimination against women and girls, provide them equal access to resources, and empower them via learning. This could consist of focused initiatives like mentorship programs, scholarships for females, and campaigns opposing gender prejudice and stereotypes in the classroom.

Invest resources to improve rural regions' educational infrastructure to ensure that all children, regardless of where they live, have access to high-quality education. This could involve constructing new educational institutions, renovating current ones, and offering guidance and assistance to teachers in remote areas.

Adopt measures to reduce socioeconomic inequalities including income disparity, housing insecurity, and access to healthcare that have an influence on academic performance. This might involve taking steps to give low-income families financial support, increase access to social services and healthcare, and develop affordable housing choices for families with students.

Create policies that support cultural diversity and inclusion in educational environments, such as curricular changes, teacher training in cultural competency, and programs to honor and conserve cultural heritage. Including a variety of viewpoints and experiences into the curriculum, supporting students from marginalized backgrounds, and fostering inclusive learning environments where all students are treated with respect and worth are some ways to do this.

Students should get priority assistance with their mental health and well-being, especially in metropolitan settings where stress levels may be greater. This could involve increasing access to mental health services, implementing stress management programs, and creating supportive environments that promote positive mental health outcomes.

policies that support sustainable urban development which maintain a balance between social justice, environmental preservation, and economic prosperity. This might involve making improvements to the infrastructure of public transportation, cutting carbon emissions, and establishing green spaces in metropolitan areas to improve the quality of life and lessen the negative effects of increasing urbanization.

To create evidence-based policies and programs that address the complex issues facing education in urban and rural contexts, policymakers, educators, researchers, and community stakeholders should be encouraged to collaborate and share information. To share resources, exchange best practices, and develop the ability for efficient policy implementation, this may require forming partnerships between governmental organizations, educational institutions, non-profit organizations, and community organizations.

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